

Tradition Vs Modernity in *A Silence of Desire* by Kamala Markandaya

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Introduction :

Literature is an artistic expression that is known and thought in the world. It appeals in the widest of human interests and the simplest of human emotions. It is occupied chiefly with elementary passions and emotion- love and hatred, joy and sorrow, fear and faith, which are essential parts of our human nature. Indian English literature or otherwise called Indian writing in English refers to the writers in India, who write in the English language and whose native or co-native language could be one of the languages of India. It has a relatively short but highly charged history.

Women writers have also played a prominent role in the area of Indian English Literature. They get inspiration from their predecessors and emerge out as new women, fully aware of their identities, rights, duties as well as their limitations. They have their own view point about life and do not need a male looking glass to view the matters of their concern.

During the post-Independence period, a number of women writers descended on the literary scene such as Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala, Nayantara

Sahgal, Anita Desai, and Shashi Deshpande. They are more sensitive in describing the lives concerning women than the male writers. Their novels project female experiences, social situations and criticism. Meena Shirwadkar remarks, “feminism, free-sex, isolation, alienation, identity crisis or an individual struggling to be oneself are some of the thematic concerns of the women novelists today.” Her novels are remarkable for their range of experience. Through her novels, Markandaya brings to light the complication of post-colonial and traditional Indian social hierarchy as well as the Implications prevalent within both systems.

In her lifetime, Kamala Markandaya published ten novels, all dealing with postcolonial themes in modern India. She is most famous for her novel *Nectar in a Sieve*, which was her third novel written, but the first novel published in 1955 *Nectar in a Sieve* became a best seller in March, 1955, earning her over \$100,000 in prizes. Her other novels include *Some Inner Fury* (1955), *A Silence of Desire* (1960), *Possession* (1963), *A Handful of Rice* (1966), *The Coffey Dams* (1969), *The Nowhere Man* (1972), *Two Virgins* (1973), *The Golden Honeycomb* (1977), and *Pleasure City* (1982/83).

Kamala Markandaya deals with the two conflicting forces of contemporary India viz., tradition and modernity in her novels. The remarkable quality that distinguishes her from other writers is her sharp awareness of shift in values that has been taking place in the post-colonial India. She understands that the clash of values stems naturally from “a nostalgic idealization of tradition and a compulsive urge for modernity”, opines Shiv. K. Kumar in *Tradition and Change in the novels of Kamala Markandaya* (85). Her awareness of the dichotomy of values is certainly related to her expatriate experience in her personal life. It will be quite pertinent to quote the words of Prem Kumar in this context. He says:

Like her, most of her characters find themselves in situations where they must confront values rooted in opposing cultural milieus, historical processes, economic systems, political ideologies, and philosophical traditions. Some are able to resolve the tensions and inequities that threaten to disintegrate psyche and spirit. Others, however, succumb to their innate weaknesses or to inexorable forces beyond their control. (22)

In *A Silence of Desire* the novelist is basically concerned with the tension between faith and reason, and spiritualism and scientific rationalism. The clash between the traditional mode of spirituality and modern materialistic attitude happens to be an important issue in the context of the Indian society of today. Karnala Markandaya with her exquisite historical vision of the transition period in Indian history portrays how these tangible and historical forces have even affected the domestic harmony of a bourgeois couple in this excellent novel. Describing the chief thematic concern of the novel, Madhusudan Prasad says:

A Silence of Desire explores the theme of the clash between traditionalism and modernism, between faith and reason represented by Sarojini and Dandekar who form a married couple in the novel. Although the theme has the immediacy of a common contemporary problem that faces most of the Indian couples, “the real achievement of the author lies in the projection of this theme through the awakening of a mind developing from thoughtless complacency to tremulous introspection.”(5)

A Silence of Desire deals with the theme of tradition and modernity through the conflict between Dandekar and Sarojini. Dandekar, a senior clerk in the government office, leads a happy life with his wife Sarojini and three children. When Sarojini secretly visits the Swami to have the growth in her womb cured, Dandekar begins to suspect his wife having an affair with the Swami and tries to check her from going to him. She, instead, has so much faith in the Swami’s power of healing that she refuses to go to the hospital for her treatment. Dandekar then tries to dislodge the Swami from his ashram. Finally, Sarojini agrees to undergo the operation in the hospital and is cured of her disease. Thus the whole story revolves round the conflict between faith and reason, superstition and science, religion and materialism, and Eastern backwardness and western progress.

The conflict between the faith of Sarojini and the reason of Dandekar does not end here but crops up again when for the treatment of her tumor Sarojini goes to the Swami without telling her husband who has no faith in such things. But when Dandekar begins to suspect her character because of her stealthy movements, she makes a clean breast of her visits to the Swami, adding that the main reason of her not disclosing them to him was her fear that he might stop her from going to the Swami, Sarojini further remarks:

You would have sent me to a hospital instead called me superstitious, a fool, because I have beliefs that you cannot share. You wouldn't have let me be no! You would have reasoned with me until I lost my faith, because faith and reason don't go together, and without faith I shall not be healed. (SD 2)

Markandaya is not trying to advocate blind faith in the Swami's powers but is making efforts to prove the Swami's genuineness. This is achieved by making the Swami leave the town and by sending Sarojini to the hospital. Again, Sarojini's acquiescence to go to the hospital is not a complete negation of faith and an acceptance of reason. Even behind the act of reason there lurks her unshakable faith. When Dandekar assures Sarojini that she will be cured without the presence of the Swami, she remarks:

"I know," she answered. "He said I would be, and not to hold back when the time came. I'm not afraid now of knives or doctors, or what they may do. All will be well. He said so." (SD 218)

Although the Swami is not able to cure the growth in Sarojini's womb, yet he is successful in preparing her mentally to undergo the operation and assuring her of its success, "Faith healing," says Margaret P. Joseph, "depends; it seems more on the faith of the sick person than on the power of the healer." (3) And so much faith has Sarojini in the Swami that she might have gone to Death itself, had it been his desire. Dandekar confesses this fact to Chari, his boss, when he contends,

"My wife is part of me now didn't realize it in all the years it has been happening, but I know now that without her I'm not whole." (SD 196)

This conflict between Dandekar's body and spirit is a part of the conflict between Eastern backwardness and Western progress. Markandaya throws more light on this aspect through harangue between Dandekar and Wilson. It is true that Dandekar is not completely a traditional man for we have seen his opposition to Sarojini's reposing faith in the Swami and her belief in getting cured by blessings rather than by surgical operation. But there are a place where Dandekar appears to have some of his roots still in the traditional ideas and as such believes in stars and horoscopes. But Wilson, being an English man, is unable to understand how man's life can be interpreted in terms of stars 'Stars? Horoscopes?' he sarcastically asks

Dandekar. “Do you really think all that glory was created in order that some measly little priest can mumble in your ear how many brats your wife is going to have?” (SD 189)

Dandekar, who feels insulted by this remark, retorts that the universe is to be taken as a whole in which each part influences the other and therefore nothing exists by itself implying thereby that as the distant moon can create rise and fall in the ocean, so the stars can also determine the destiny of human beings. Dandekar, who is partly traditional and partly modern, is orthodox in certain matters.

Sum up :

In short, the world of *A Silence of Desire* is the world of science and superstition carefully balanced, each one having its own separate entity. Markandaya does not raise one prominently up by pulling down the other. Her attitude is that of reconciliation between the two. *A Silence of Desire* deals with the theme of clash between faith and reason through the conflict between Dandekar and Sarojini. Finally, Sarojini agrees to undergo an operation in the nursing home and is ultimately cured of her disease.

References :

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